

A methodological approach to aggregate multiple measures of hospital quality using variance-based weights

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ABSTRACT

Objective: This study presents an econometric approach to measure hospital performance and potentially compare quality of care between different health care systems. The method is based on the simultaneous estimation of accelerated failure time (AFT) models across four cardiovascular interventions and two outcomes. The two-stage variance-based weights approach has several advantages: first, the extent to which an indicator contributes to the aggregate index depends on the amount of its variance, second the risk adjustment reduces a potential hospital selection bias. The method was restricted to acute cardiovascular events occurred in Germany from 2005 to 2016.

Methods: Data were extracted from a large German sickness fund and further information on hospitals were obtained from Inkar databases. The two-stage regression approach estimated hospital performance over four specific indicators for Germany: ST elevation (STEMI), non-ST elevation (NSTEMI) acute myocardial infarction (AMI) in primary or secondary diagnosis, Coronary Bypass Surgery (CABG or bypass) and Cardiac Resynchronization (ICD/CRT or HZM). Mortality and hospital readmissions were used as outcomes and severity of readmission was weighted for the length of hospital stay. The hospital estimates obtained in the first stage were aggregated in the second-stage. The AFT models were fitted by maximum likelihood (Newton Raphson algorithm). Results were normalized into an index range from zero to one. The sensitivity analysis tested the internal validity simulating several scenarios.

Results: Overall, 137,046 episodes occurred in 446 hospitals that fulfilled the defined inclusion criteria, 551 patients died, and 136,495 were readmitted; we categorized 22,967 as CABG, 41,481 as ICD/CRT, 28,618 as STEMI, and 43,980 as NSTEMI. There were 36,259 right-censored observations related to death and 100,787 right-censored observations related to readmission. The precision-based weights were higher for mortality than readmission in case of CABG, ICD/CRT, and AMI-STEMI; conversely, NSTEMI exhibited a larger weight in case of readmission. Correlations between the intervention-specific indices and the aggregated index were highly significant ($p < 0.001$) for all interventions with Spearman's Rho above 0.5. Additionally, mean standardized 95% confidence intervals were larger for STEMI and NSTEMI specific indices.

Discussion: Overall AFT is more efficient compared with GLM models that rely on dichotomized data, additionally, SUR allows for correlation between different outcomes. Although the method can still raise issues pertaining to unobserved effects, endogeneity and variability of treatment quality across providers and over time, we consider the approach robust and *'fairly rich'* in front of further residual stochastic variability. The index can be extended to further clinical areas and adapted to different healthcare systems.